

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 1.1

Project Management

Handbook

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- PU:** Public (must be available on the website)
- CO:** Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- Cl:** Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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SUMMARY

NEWSERA will analyse and evaluate the complex and multidirectional science communication strategies, including digital and non-digital ones, addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders in citizen science projects across Europe as the new paradigm for science communication.

The overall aim of NEWSERA is to demonstrate the virtues of citizen science as an inclusive, broad and powerful science communication mechanism that can allow to increase trust in science communication and, in turn, in science at large, while opening up science and innovation to society, raising awareness and educating in science, and reducing the chances of incurring in fake news by promoting critical thinking.

The present document provides an **overview of the management structures and procedures that will ensure an efficient execution and high quality excellent implementation of the NEWSERA project** and thus contribute to the production of high quality project results and outcomes. The aim is to provide the project beneficiaries with a handbook that indicates the management structures, tasks and responsibilities at all levels in project execution.

The established procedures' main goal is to assure quality implementation of NEWSERA. Those are based on the general principles and policies defined in underlying basic regulations (H2020-SwafS-2018-2020, Science with and for Society), EU rules for participation in Horizon 2020, contracts and agreements and official guidelines. Likewise, the general principles for project execution have been defined in the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action and in the Consortium Agreement provisions. The project handbook shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium or with the European Commission (EC), or any of the EC guidelines for project implementation and documentation. If any inconsistencies appear between these documents, the following protocol of order will be applied:

1. Grant Agreement with EC and its annexes
2. Consortium Agreement
3. Project Handbook [present document]

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1 Project management structure

The NEWSERA organisational structure is informed by the successful management of previous European funded collaborative projects.

To ensure clear responsibilities and transparent communication flows, the following management structure has been agreed on and will be implemented throughout the project (see figure 1).

Figure 1. The NEWSERA Management structure

The management structure presented has been designed in order to:

- Manage and support the full consortium team in terms of relevance of the work, its scientific quality and its coherence.
- Support the full consortium team in terms of research and innovation management, allowing the consortium to respond to external or internal opportunities.
- Manage and support the full consortium team financially and administratively in terms of keeping to timescale, effective use and suitable reporting of budget resources.
- Liaise effectively with the European Commission on all matters of strategy, relevance, scientific quality, timescale, administration, reporting, and budget.

The management structure will be explained in detail in the following sections.

1.1 Project coordination

The Project Coordinator is responsible for the overall line of actions, the day-to-day management of the project with the support of the Project Manager and a high quality and timely delivery of outcomes.

The Project Coordinator will be the intermediary between the partners and the European Commission and shall ensure that all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement are performed - including monitoring the compliance of the partners with their obligations, an excellent project implementation, submitting the deliverables timely and with high quality as well as reports to the EC, and ensuring that all payments are made to the other beneficiaries without unjustified delay. The Project Coordinator will also ensure daily communication between partners and compliance with the internal quality processes.

NEWSERA Project Coordinator is [MSc. Rosa Arias](#). She is the CEO & Founder of [Science for Change](#), a startup born to exploit the project results of the [D-NOSES Project](#) (SwafS-23-2017), which she coordinates within Ibercivis. She is also the creator of the citizen science [App OdourCollect](#), to collaboratively build odour maps from affected communities by odour issues to promote dialogue and co-create solutions with relevant stakeholders.

She has experience as odour expert for 15 years and has worked as Project Manager and Olfactometry Laboratory Manager in 2 of the 3 main companies dealing with odour pollution in Spain (the Odournet Group and Business Strengths Engineering). She has created the citizen science App OdourCollect to empower citizens suffering from odour nuisance, after facing terrible situations in local communities during all her years of professional experience. She has more than 10 years' experience coordinating European projects (FP7, H2020, LIFE+, etc.). She has previously coordinated and participated in other H2020 projects in the fields of bioplastics, waste and circular economy, such as the BBI POLYBIOSKIN, ECOBULK and DAFIA projects. She has also coordinated the Spanish hub of the HYPATIA project for "la Caixa" Foundation (RRI Tools coordinators), on attracting girls towards STEM careers, and has successfully coordinated the CLIMADAT project on climate change research (6M€), also for "la Caixa" Foundation.

The NEWSERA Project Manager is [Oriol Agulló](#). He is Communication & Project Manager at SfC. He is a Chemist with Masters' in History of Science and Environmental Communication and Education. He has a long history of participation in sustainability projects and environmental communication. He has devised and led projects such as the Map Barcelona + Sustainable, a collaborative map of the environmental initiatives of the city of Barcelona; Energia Activa, a project for the insertion and labour recycling of people over 45; Library of Things of Barcelona, the first in Spain; Cafacció, a project of social innovation to tackle energy poverty; COCREA, a process of co-creation with scientists, civil society and educators to address challenges such as green gentrification in Barcelona. Mr. Oriol Agulló also has a long experience in writing articles on science, sustainability and social transformation, in media such as La Directa, Sostenible.cat, Món Sostenible

or Crític. He has worked as a communication manager in public sustainability centres, in NGOs specialized in energy and in companies of museography and scientific dissemination.

1.2 Executive management

1.2.1 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is represented by the project partners together with the Project Coordinator. It serves as key body to disseminate information, facilitate mutual learning and dialogues, sharing of experiences and meeting between people from different disciplines. In particular the General Assembly aim is to: 1) discuss and evaluate the detailed work plans of activities; 2) discuss and evaluate the progress of the work undertaken; 3) discuss the inputs from the Mutual Learning process and the participatory activities (#CitSciComm Labs) involved in the actions.

Periodic project meetings for the GA encounters have been scheduled: the kick-off meeting (M2), the Periodic Consortium Meetings (M6, M11, M18, M22, M27) and the final meeting (M35). The original plan of the GA was that three of the #CitSciComm Labs would be happening at the same time as the GA (with the aim of optimizing travel costs and human resources) and two would be held in Brussels for strategic and financial reasons. Following the plan, the NEWSERA kick-off meeting (Barcelona, 4-6 February 2020) blended a GA meeting with the consortium partners and the Project Officer, together with two days of participatory workshops that simulated the functioning of the future NEWSERA #CitSciComm Labs.

Due to the COVID-19 crisis, the project has gained a high degree of uncertainty in its work plan. The NEWSERA team has had to rethink the GA meetings, the functioning of the #CitSciComm Labs and the whole project management and contingency management plan in order to reduce the COVID-19 crisis impacts, to adapt it to a more remotely-run project management and to prevent a possible repetition of similar situations in the future.

The GA meetings have been rescheduled (to be held at M10, M14, M18, M22 and M28) and have been moved to remote meetings, with the possibility of doing them face-to-face if the future situation with the pandemic allows. The GA meetings will be held prior to each #CitSciComm Lab with guides and activities to guarantee the coordination among Consortium members during the Labs and to define their specific objectives, pilots involved and participants to be invited from the citizen science community and the science communication / data journalism communities. The GA meetings will be run using the Zoom Conference Tool and online collaborative tools such as Padlet.

The #CitSciComm Labs sessions have also been transformed into a three national face-to-face (combined with remote attendance) cycle of labs, with stakeholder-tailored-workshops, and with remote participation. Like this, the five

rounds of #CitSciComm Labs (happening at M10, M14, M18, M22 and M28) will be done in parallel in each of the NEWSERA countries (Italy, Spain and Portugal) and in a cascade fashion for the different targeted stakeholders (policy makers, citizens, scientists, industry and SMEs, and data journalists), with a separation of around 3 weeks per stakeholder type. Depending on the advancement of the project, the objectives of the #CitSciComm Labs, the pilots and the participants to be invited will be defined during the previous GA meeting.

Each partner representative in the GA will be included in the project contact list (under the title of all-newsera@scienceforchange.eu) for communication efficiency. Representatives are intended to be maintained throughout the project, if possible. Any change in a partner's representatives to the GA should be informed by writing to the Project Coordinator at least 10 days before a Project meeting takes place, indicating the reason for substitution, identifying the new representative and explaining whether the substitution will be temporary or permanent.

1.2.2 Executive Board (EB)

It is constituted by the Project Coordinator and one representative per project partner, and it serves as the main decision body of the consortium. The EB is chaired by the Project Coordinator and it is in charge of the overall direction and technical assessment of the project. The assigned members of the EB will have sufficient seniority to take binding decisions without referring back to higher authority at their employing organisation. The group will: 1) foster a fruitful interaction among partners; 2) guarantee an efficient information flow through all members; 3) supervise the executive plan for any specific activity set-up by the WP teams; 4) decide general and specific strategies in the project evolution; 5) monitor the work in progress by checking the achievement of tasks and deliverables.

The Executive Board is responsible for coordinating and fixing the dates and logistics of project meetings; the exact dates are fixed at least 1 month ahead of time. The EB meetings take place in parallel to GA meetings (M10, M14, M18, M22 and M28) and also once per month by teleconference/Zoom (every first Thursday of each month), or more often if needed/requested. The agenda is also generated by the Executive Board and it is distributed to the beneficiaries at least 14 calendar days prior to the meeting (7 calendar days in case of extraordinary meeting). Expenses can be charged against the project. Meeting minutes can be found on the shared workspace (Google Drive).

The EB will evaluate the results from each WP and of the overall project at key milestones during the project execution, it will make the appropriate decisions about external collaborations and agreements. The Executive Board also supervises the policy of dissemination of the project results. The EB takes any appropriate decision on the budget, and any matter related to the contract, as specified in the Consortium Agreement. Quorum of at least 50% of the EB

members will be necessary before taking any decision. Decisions will be taken by simple majority, and the coordinator will have the casting vote.

1.2.3 Sounding Board

The NEWSERA Sounding Board is composed by the members of the five #CitSciComm Labs (at least six members per Lab, two per NEWSERA country, consisting of renowned science communicators and data journalists). It has two key goals in NEWSERA:

- ensure the soundness of NEWSERA' methodological approach.
- support the Community of Practice in the definition and evaluation of the new concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism to advance the state-of-the-art in science communication.

Composition and engagement of the Sounding Board has been affected by the COVID-19 crisis. A more local strategy to engage key actors from each Consortium country is taking place, as well as to introduce online dynamics for allowing remote participation and for strengthening the relationships between them, thus promoting mutual learning. The final composition of each Lab and the SB will be defined through actions T3.1 and T3.3, supported by T6.5, and will be adopted to the citizen science pilots to be invited to the #CitSciComm Labs, depending on their specific communication needs with their target audiences.

1.2.4 NEWSERA Innovation Committee (IC)

The Innovation Committee (IC) will deal with the innovation activities of NEWSERA, namely Communication and Data Journalism management, Science Communication management, Citizen Science and Engagement management, Training management, Gender and Inclusiveness management. All the managers will constitute the Management Support Team. The IC will meet face-to-face coinciding with each WP meeting. Follow-up meetings by teleconference/Skype will be organized monthly. Quorum of at least 2/3 of the IC members will be necessary before taking any decision. Decisions will be taken by 2/3 majority. The following Innovation Managers are appointed:

- **Communication & Data Journalism Manager:** Dr. Elisabetta Tola from Formicablu
- **Science Communication Manager:** Dr. Federico Neresini from UNIPD
- **Citizen Science, Engagement, Gender and Inclusiveness Manager:** Ms. Nora Salas Seoane from Ibercivis
- **Teaching Manager:** Dr. Cristina Luis from Faculty of Sciences, University of Lisbon
- **Data Manager:** Dr. Francisco Sanz from Ibercivis
- **Ethics Manager:** Ms. Maite Pelacho from Ibercivis
- **IPR & Exploitation Manager:** Ms. Rosa Arias from SfC

1.2.5 Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders

The NEWSERA Work Plan is structured in 8 Work Packages (WP). Each work package has a **Work Package Leader** appointed, who is responsible for the progress within the work package. WP Leaders have contact with the coordinator on a regular basis during virtual EB monthly meetings, in order to ensure the monitoring of the project, but shall also get in direct contact by mail, phone or other means whenever necessary.

The Work Package Leaders are responsible for coordinating the group of activities under their Work Package, monitor their execution, and reporting regularly their progress and any other appropriate information to the Executive Board and the Coordinator. WP Leaders interact with Task Leaders to ensure communication among all the people involved. **Task Leaders** are responsible for the accomplishment of specific tasks under their work package, and more importantly of coordinating the work of a small team of people according to the Work Plan. They report to the WP Leader, in order to ensure the effective information flow and monitoring of the work progress.

Task Leaders coordinate the work among contributors inside the task; they will organize short and medium work planning via meetings, revisions, etc., to timely fulfil deliverables and milestones. They supervise and assess task progress against task objectives, handle deviations and guide the task contributors to keep on track. They report to the WP leader on task progress and provide on time inputs to activities, planning and progress reports as requested and agreed; they will also ensure that task-related information is up-to-date on the shared workspace (Google Drive).

Contributors will participate in the short and medium-term task planning (activities, timing, etc.) and will proactively ensure they stay up to date on progress and methods; they will actively contribute to the task implementation with inputs and ideas via regular meetings and other online interchanges, and also participate in the writing of the deliverables.

In the following table, WP Leaders and Task Leaders are appointed:

WP	Task Title	Lead Partner
WP1	Coordination and Project Management	SfC
	1.1 Project Coordination and Administrative Management	SfC
	1.2 Financial and progress reporting	SfC
	1.3 Internal communication, quality assurance and risk management	SfC
	1.4 Interaction with NEWSERA governance bodies	SfC
WP2	Analysis of Citizen Science as a Science Communication tool	UNIPD
	2.1 Analysis of science communication strategies for citizen science projects, engaged under EU-Citizen.Science	UNIPD

	2.2	Definition of impact indicators of effectiveness in terms of quality of perception	UNIPD
	2.3	Evaluation of the current impact	IBERCIVIS
	2.4	Selection of NEWSERA pilots to be involved in the #CitSciComm Labs	SfC
	Co-designing innovative strategies in Citizen Science Communication		FECYT
WP3	3.1	Establishing the NEWSERA Citizen Science Communication Labs addressed to quadruple helix stakeholders	SfC
	3.2	Co-designing innovative strategies to improve Citizen Science Communication through the Labs	UNIPD
	3.3	Establishing the NEWSERA Citizen Science Communication Labs addressed to Data Science Journalists	FORMICABLU
	3.4	Advancing the concept of Citizen Science Journalism	FORMICABLU
	3.5	Informal and formal training mechanisms and evaluation of incentives	FC.ID
	3.6	#CitSciComm to fight against misinformation in the post-factual era	FECYT
	The NEWSERA Pilots: Implementing the concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism		SfC
WP4	4.1	Coordination of the NEWSERA Citizen Science Communication Labs	SfC
	4.2	NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab addressed to citizen scientists and society at large	UNIPD
	4.3	NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab addressed to career scientists	FC.ID
	4.4	NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab addressed to policy makers	FECYT
	4.5	NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab addressed to industry and SMEs	SfC
	4.6	NEWSERA #CitSciComm Lab addressed to data science journalists	FORMICABLU
	Evaluation and impact assessment: the legacy of NEWSERA		FC.ID
WP5	5.1	Co-designing indicators to assess the concepts of Citizen Science Communication and Citizen Science Journalism	UNIPD
	5.2	Iterative assessment of the impact of the new communication strategies for each stakeholder group	IBERCIVIS
	5.3	Barriers detected for increased effectiveness and improved perception of trust	IBERCIVIS
	5.4	NEWSERA replicability guidelines & policy briefs	FECYT
WP6	Dissemination and Communication Actions		FORMICABLU

	6.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	FORMICABLU
	6.2	Visual Identity and Interactive project website	FORMICABLU
	6.3	Cross-media Production	FORMICABLU
	6.4	Offline dissemination and communication activities	FORMICABLU
	6.5	Networking with #SciComm, #CitSci and RRI projects for increased outreach	SfC
WP7	Ethics and Data Protection strategies in NEWSERA		IBERCIVIS
	7.1	Identifying ethical aspects as a cross-cutting issue in NEWSERA actions	IBERCIVIS
	7.2	Data Management Plan (DMP)	IBERCIVIS
	7.3	Procedures to identify, recruit and engage research participants	IBERCIVIS
	7.4	Requirement for Personal Data Protection (POPD)	IBERCIVIS
WP8	Ethics requirements		SfC

Table 1. work Plan structure, WPs Leaders and Task Leaders in NEWSERA

1.3 Mailing lists and document exchange platform

To facilitate written communication, an e-mail distribution list has been created. Any doubt, question and notification (e.g. of intended deliverables and/or tasks) shall be directed to “all-news-era@scienceforchange.eu”. The EB will then coordinate the actions that need to be taken.

An appropriate shared workspace (“NEWSERA network”) has been created by the Project Coordinator. This workspace uses the Google Drive repository (with servers located in Europe) and it is used to facilitate the accessibility and exchange of the whole NEWSERA documents. It incorporates collaborative tools to an easy-development of those documents. GDPR Compliance is carefully sought within the shared workspace, to which only NEWSERA partners can access.

1.3.1 Code of conduct

When sending an email to the NEWSERA partners using the “all-news-era@scienceforchange.eu” mailing list, the prefix “[NEWSERA]” is automatically added to the subject line. When sharing documents over email, documents should be linked (from the shared workspace) and attached to emails for easy reference. Example: “Please find attached and in folder...”

1.4 Conflict resolution

Any conflicts concerning technical issues will be resolved by the Project Coordinator. In the event that the coordinator is unable to achieve consensus, an independent referee (a member of the Sounding Board) will be appointed whose

judgment will be considered conclusive. If the dispute persists, the consortium will inform the project officer, soliciting the advice of reviewers, and call for an additional meeting with members of the Sounding Board.

2 Administrative project management

The NEWSERA approach to project management is described in this section. Useful information on interesting administrative aspects of project management can be obtained from the documents listed in section 5: References.

Figure 2 shows the NEWSERA Gantt diagram, where all project actions are calendarised. The execution calendar's reference units are in M (Months), with M01 starting on the 1st of January 2020. The administrative execution period is fractionated into 2 main reporting periods (RP):

1. **RP1:** from month 1 to month 15
2. **RP2:** from month 16 to month 36

Figure 2. The NEWSERA GANTT

Within the project's execution period, the reporting, deliverables and planning cycles consist of (see also the corresponding following sections in the present handbook).

2.1 Resource reporting

Purpose

For the justification of personnel costs and the support of the project audit, partners are required to maintain monthly (at least) time recording and should

provide periodic financial reports as requested below on effort devoted to the project and its WPs (Effort Report). Effort reports are used to control progress versus planning and provide input for the periodic management reports to the EC.

Time recording (timesheets)

Records of the hours dedicated to NEWSERA during each calendar month of the execution period by all staff of every partner (signed paper copies or any electronic system duly liable, archived/recorded by partners for their auditing process) should be conveniently prepared and stored. Time sheets are not deliverable items and they do not have to be submitted to the EC (excepting during audit processes). Each partner is in principle free to use its own model/system, but the Project Coordinator will provide a suitable template by M9.

Resource reports

The Effort Reports are based on the time recording data and summarising the information contained therein. This information is needed to develop future action plans and to verify that the project goes in the right way relating to resources consumption.

Effort Reports need to be generated and submitted to the Project Coordinator, with copy to the involved WP Leaders, for periods of specified months (M9, M15, M22, M29, M36) using the template provided by the Coordinator hosted on the shared work space (Google Drive). Although these reports may be preliminary estimates and must not be based on closed account statements, they should be as accurate as possible in order to facilitate general resource control.

The reports are to be sent to the Project Manager by email maximum 1 month after the corresponding reporting period. The Project Coordinator will check the information against the work plan and create a deviation report (.xls sheets). This report is sent to WP Leaders one week after reception of the Partners' reports. WP Leaders check the report and identify problems and risks to the EB and the Coordinator. The effort reporting periods for NEWSERA are:

- *January 2020 – September 2020 (M9);*
- *October 2020 – March 2021 (M15) – in preparation for EC RP1 (M15);*
- *April 2021 – October 2021 (M22);*
- *November 2021 - May 2022 (M29);*
- *June 2022 to December 2022 (M36) - in preparation for EC RP2 (M36).*

2.2 Project deliverable generation

General

In this subsection, the project deliverables generation is presented, documents arising from WPs progress, often in the form of written reports. All non-report deliverables are nevertheless to be documented in a written report on their

content and achievements, functionality, testing, limitations, and envisaged enhancements.

The responsible author will submit the deliverable to the Project Coordinator, after an internal quality assurance review, before the due date (as stated in the DoA), and following the procedure and timing detailed below (and in D1.2). Project Coordinator takes care of the submission to the EC after a final review. Deliverables are reviewed at the end of the corresponding reporting period together with the periodic reports.

Quality criteria for internal review

- **Completeness:** Content must address all aspects related to the purpose but avoid redundancy of information.
- **Accuracy:** Content must be reliable, conclusions must match results produced and take account of any assumptions made or restrictions imposed.
- **Relevance:** Content must be focused on the key issues.
- **Depth:** Content must have adequate depth but must nevertheless be presented in a concise manner.
- **Adherence to standard:** The project output has to be uniform in appearance and structure.

Format

A template with deliverable design is available on the shared workspace (Google Drive).

Procedure and timing

1) *Two months before the due date:* Project Coordinator nominates the responsible author for the specific deliverable. The WP leader and responsible author determine their responsibility, nominate the team of authors and decide the deliverable outline and how the deliverable will be produced and reviewed.

3) *One month before the due date:* Responsible author sends a first draft of the deliverable to the Project Coordinator and WP leader.

4) *No later than two weeks before the due date:* The final draft is sent to the Project Coordinator and WP Leader by the responsible author to initiate the final review process. The Project Coordinator and WP Leader send their comments to the author, who incorporates the comments and generates the final version for revision. WP leader checks format, clarifies any queries with the author and generates a final version.

5) *No later than one week before the due date:* The final version is sent by the responsible author and WP Leader to the Project Coordinator for final check and approval.

7) *Submission to EC by the Project Coordinator.* The Project Coordinator is responsible for the adequate intra-Consortium distribution of the final versions and deliverable submission.

8) The Commission evaluates the reports and deliverables in accordance with Article 22.1.2 of the Grant Agreement. It may be assisted in this task by independent experts through technical project reviews.

Deliverable amendment requests

The Project Coordinator coordinates any amendment requested by the EC and the project reviewers. Such requests are communicated to the EB. The amendment itself has to be carried out by the authors having the responsibility for the deliverable.

2.3 Periodic reports to the EC

Purpose

To provide the EC, periodically, with progress - technical, management and financial control information - is needed to justify efforts and investments, and provide reviewed detailed planning.

Components and responsibilities

- A **periodic technical report**, including an overview of progress, to be compiled by the Project Coordinator, with input from the WPs leaders and Task Leaders;
- A **periodic financial report**, compiled by the Project Coordinator, with input from all partners;
 - individual financial statements from each beneficiary;
 - an explanation of the use of resources including subcontracting;
 - a periodic summary financial statement; created automatically consolidating the individual financial statements and includes the request for interim payment.

The Project Coordinator has the overall responsibility of creating, coordinating and submitting periodic reports to the EC.

Procedure and timing

The completion of reports is aligned with the specified reporting periods (RP1 (M1 – M15) and RP2 (M16 – M36)) and the reports have to be submitted no later than 60 days after each period electronically via the Funding & Tenders Portal. All partners need to contribute to these reports and therefore need to allocate time to internal project management providing the necessary information on work progress, efforts, justification of costs and resources used.

The workflow is as follows:

- Progress is monitored continuously by the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager and the WP Leaders.
- Expenses, budget and efforts are monitored and documented continuously by each partner with the support when necessary of the Project Manager.
- Four months before of each RP deadline at the latest, the Project Coordinator informs all beneficiaries about requirements and obligations for the upcoming report, suggests a report generation work plan and provides templates. It needs to be mentioned that the description of work performed required for the technical report needs to be carried out on work package level and therefore should be supported by corresponding WP Leaders.
- One month before the EC deadline all beneficiaries and WP Leaders provide the requested input to the Project Coordinator (except final financial statements, as indicated in the following sections). With this, the Project Coordinator triggers the review process:
 - The draft report is sent to the Project Coordinator for check and approval (not later than 3 weeks before deadline).
 - The EB delivers its comments (not later than by 2 weeks before deadline).
 - The Project Coordinator informs to whom it may concern about necessary major changes, generates the final version and submits the reports including all complementary forms and material to the EC (on deadline).

Official templates and models will be available on the Google Drive shared workspace. Where deemed necessary they may be distributed in customised versions by the Project Manager.

2.3.1 Financial statements (cost statements)

Purpose

For the fulfilment of the EC requirements regarding periodic reports, every beneficiary should be familiar with the fundamental requirements of financial reporting. The Project Manager provides support in this regard, as this is critical for the due justification and reimbursement of the costs.

Shortcomings or problems in the partners reports would affect their particular payments according to EC regulations.

Components and responsibilities

- **Breakdown of costs:** Partners will send to the Project Coordinator a breakdown of costs declared in the financial individual statement. This is now a contractual obligation and therefore shall be submitted to the Project Coordinator. It shall help the Project Coordinator in the justification process and in checking the information for completeness, consistency and correctness. The main cost categories to be specified are personnel, travel,

consumables, audits, equipment, overheads and other. This information is sent to the Project Coordinator by email and will be exclusively used for checking and completing the information in the different parts of the reports. Templates will be provided by the Project Coordinator.

- **All information will ultimately be submitted and “signed” by the eligible representatives in the Funding and Tenders Portal.** All beneficiaries - including the Project Coordinator - must fill in their own financial statement, electronically sign it and submit it to the coordinator. The individual financial statement must detail the eligible costs (actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs; see Article 6 of the EC Grant Agreement) for each budget category. The beneficiaries must declare all eligible costs, even if — for actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs — they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget.

Procedure and timing

Partners are required to provide the Project Coordinators with the abovementioned breakdown of costs no later than 30 calendar days after the end of the reporting period. Templates will be provided by the Project Coordinator.

2.4 Final report

Purpose

To provide the EC with the overall project overview and justification, with special emphasis on publishable results and relevant socio-economic impact - the final report is submitted together with the periodic report for the last reporting period.

Components and responsibilities

In addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, Project Coordinator must submit the final report within 60 days following the end of the last reporting period.

The final report must include the following:

- a **‘final technical report’** with a summary for publication containing:
 - an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - the conclusions on the action, and
 - the socio-economic impact of the action;
- a **‘final financial report’** containing:
 - a ‘final summary financial statement’, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and
 - a ‘certificate on the financial statements’ (drawn up in accordance with the Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement) for each beneficiary, if it requests a total contribution of EUR 325.000 or more, as

reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices (see Article 5.2 and Article 6.2 of the Grant Agreement).

2.4.1 Certificates on Financial Statements (audit certificates)

Audit Certificates are now formally called **Certificates on Financial Statements (CFS)**.

A Certificate on the Financial Statements (drawn up in accordance with the Annex 5 of the GA) is mandatory for each beneficiary, if it requests a total contribution of EUR 325 000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices

Each relevant beneficiary shall provide a certificate prepared and certified by an external auditor, certifying that the costs incurred during that period meet the conditions required by the agreement. The certificate should expressly state the amounts that were subject to verification and must be forwarded in the form of a detailed description verified as factual by the external auditor (Annex 5 of the EC Grant Agreement). Where third parties' costs are claimed under the contract, such costs shall be audited in accordance with the provisions of the contract.

The reasonable cost of this certification, when compulsory, is an eligible cost under the activity relating to Management of the consortium and are then 100% refundable (except for VAT) by the Commission within its contribution.

Each beneficiary is free to choose any qualified external auditor, including its usual external auditor, provided that it meets the cumulative following professional requirements:

1. The external auditor must be independent from the beneficiary;
2. The external auditor must be qualified to carry out statutory audits of accounting documents in accordance with the current EC directive on statutory audits of annual accounts and consolidated accounts or similar national regulations (any European Union legislation replacing this Directive).

Certification by external auditors according to the contract does not diminish the liability of beneficiaries according to the contract nor the rights of the Community with respect to carrying out its own controls and audits and any other right arising from the EC Grant Agreement.

See also Annex 5 of the EC contract and the [EC guidance on audits](#).

2.5 Project reviews

Purpose

Periodic project reviews and a final project review is carried out by the EC through external reviewers to assess the work carried out and the results obtained (includes review of the deliverables) and, if necessary, to provide recommendations and reorientations that may be required.

The review principally assesses:

- the degree of fulfilment of the project work plan and the deliverables for the period;
- the continued relevance of the objectives and breakthrough potential with respect to the scientific and industrial state of the art;
- the resources employed and other management aspects of the project;
- the beneficiaries contributions and integration within the project;
- the plan for using and disseminating the knowledge.

Components and responsibilities

- **Report and deliverables review:** EC reviews through external experts the project progress (periodic reports and eventual additional information) and results (deliverables and dissemination and exploitation activities).
- **Review meeting between EC, the Coordinator and those partners involved in technical presentations or representing partner's interests.** Periodic review meetings usually take place after the delivery of periodic reports and before the end of the review period. The final review meeting could take place (at EC discretion) before the final reports are delivered to maintain the possibility to generate input for them¹. The Project Coordinator coordinates, requests and submits eventual additional information and material, calls the necessary beneficiaries and invites consortium members.

Procedure and timing

The EC sets the procedure for the hearing and informs the Project Coordinator. The external reviewers are determined by the EC before the first review. They usually remain reviewers throughout the project.

The Consortium may reject a reviewer through written declaration and justification. The outcome of the review is communicated in writing to the Coordinator after the submission of periodic reports and corresponding deliverables. The outcome may include technical recommendations to be taken into account in the project's planning for the work. In some specific cases the consortium, through the EB,

¹ The fact that this takes place after the execution (and financed) period of the project has to be taken into account as cost therefore cannot be charged against the project and eventual project bound work contracts may have finished by then.

would need to present an amended plan which, on approval by the Commission, would be appended to the DoA, Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement²

At the end of each reporting period, the Commission shall evaluate and approve project reports and deliverables and disburse the corresponding payments within 90 days of their receipt (see Article 21.4 of the EC Grant Agreement).

2.6 Cost reimbursement and payments

The Project Coordinator exclusively receives all project related payments from the EC. On reception of any payment the Project Coordinator, duly and without delay, processes the distribution of the financial contributions to the partners according to his EC-contractual obligations and in agreement with the financial plan of NEWSERA project and the dispositions of the Consortium Agreement.

2.7 Contract amendments

Contract amendments are coordinated by the Project Coordinator. Changes affecting the contract could lead to a major review of the DoA and the GPF (Grant Preparation Forms) and will therefore require a high level of interaction with the EC Project Officer and the project partners through the EB.

Events that require or trigger contract amendments are:

- Beneficiaries joining or leaving the consortium (it includes changes at legal and financial level of the current beneficiaries)
- Relevant modifications of the budget and / or its distribution (beneficiaries are allowed to slightly transfer budget between different activities and between themselves in so far as the work is carried out as foreseen in the DoA)
- Relevant changes in the detailed work plan
- Modifications in the coordination and management structure and/or their working principles as specified in the Grant Agreement and/or its annexes.

Relocation or resignation of key personnel (explicitly listed in the DoA) usually does not directly lead to an amendment of the contract if it does not require the change of budgets, objectives, the work plan or the inclusion / exclusion of a beneficiary. The Project Coordinator has to notify such changes to the Project Officer in formal written form (letter) and has to take care that the next DoA update reflects the change. Changes in other staff, students, etc., that affect the project need to be reported to the corresponding WP Leader with copy to the EB.

A document for tracking proposals for amendments can be found on the shared workspace (Google Drive).

² If no recommendations are made, then the original plan as submitted with the Periodic reports will be appended to the Grant Agreement Annex 1.

2.8 Management communication

General

The Project Manager (representing the Coordinator) maintains contact to all partners and stays in permanent close contact with the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator is responsible for maintaining the contact to the Project Officer and the EC and of communicating relevant issues to the corresponding beneficiaries.

Coordination of the monthly meetings

The Project Manager organizes coordination meetings (in the form of conference calls) with the EB to exchange information and coordinate administrative decisions and actions. These meetings have shared agendas and minutes. Usually there are taking place during the **first Thursday of each month at 11.30 am CET using the BlueJeans/Zoom Conference Call Platform** but may be organized in other days for special deliberations or key decisions. All meeting agendas and minutes can be found on the shared workspace (Google Drive).

Phone and email communication

The EB generally use phone and voice over IP (VOIP, e.g. Zoom or BlueJeans) communication for discussing ideas, determining who should be included in a discussion and reaching consensus. They generally use email communication for recording consensus, recording actions to be taken, confirming decisions in writing and sending documents for review.

Sharing documentation

All project documentation is posted onto the NEWSERA project shared workspace (Google Drive).

Style guide

A style guide is used to ensure that content distinguishes the NEWSERA brand and is cohesive. Principles, templates and other documents are deployed at D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan.

2.9 Document repository, specification format and versioning

NEWSERA's technical documents are stored in four classes of repositories:

- Personal computers and personal cloud systems (out of the scope of this document);

- Partner organisations' servers and cloud systems (out of the scope of this document);
- NEWSERA's Google Drive cloud system (also accessible via the NEWSERA shared workspace Google Drive);
- Other storage systems (e.g., paper) (out of the scope of this document).

Google Drive

NEWSERA's Google Drive cloud system site is a private repository accessible only by projects participants and managed by SfC.

Any format can be used for documents, but it was decided to use Google formats, because of online collaborative reasons and the compatibility with Office versions: Google documents can be edited collaboratively online in real time by various users and allows tracking management and finding out historical comments by each contributor.

3 Internal communication and dissemination

3.1 Approval and responsibilities

Purpose

It is important that the consortium creates a corporate image of trust and confidence. It has public responsibilities (inform, justify, inter-project collaboration, innovate, protect interests of third parties) and internal interests (individual and group visibility, protections of own interests, protection of knowledge, economic and scientific exploitations) that have to be matched.

For that reason it is of high importance to take only well coordinated actions on major external communication, dissemination and exploitation issues.

- Dissemination planning is the responsibility of WP6. Dissemination actions are aligned with the established plan.
- Common and project-wide exploitation strategies shall be defined in WP6.
- Coordination and support: Coordination of all related activities and actions is done by the Project Coordinator. The EB may give support where required in any related activity.
- Internal information policy: all major activities get, when approved, coordination support from the EB where necessary and, when carried out, are reported to the EB.
- Confidentiality: The consortium signed confidentiality clauses with the Consortium Agreement that have to be respected at any time and for any public or consortium level disclosure of information.

Components and approval

All major communication and dissemination activities should look for prior approval by the decision making components of the NEWSERA management structure.

- **Foreground protection and exploitation:** General provisions, rules of ownership and protection of knowledge are regulated in the Consortium Agreement. In general there is no approval necessary for related actions as ownership is with individual partners or joint ownership of a group of partners who have agreed upon the conditions. Only in case of disputes, would the involved partners appeal to the Project Coordinator. It is important, however, that for project documentation and general coordination reasons the partners report their intentions on any such activity to the EB including a course description of an intended/actual patent application or similar IP measure.
- **Publications:** By publication we refer to any abstract, scientific paper, oral presentation, press release or similar that aims at disseminating NEWSERA foreground in public. The general provisions for project related publications are fixed in the CA. There is no need for approval, however, includes the right of all involved partners and the Commission to object to any publication if they consider that the protection of their Knowledge would be adversely affected. This means that any intended publication has to be provided to the Partners through the EB before the intended publication date or deadline. This also will help the EB to monitor and document the public project output and to check it against dissemination plans. The EB may create during the lifetime of the project a repository of public information and material on the project web-page that is cleared of any doubts and may be used without checking. In case of any disputes the Project Coordinator is entitled to decide on the matter.
- **Publication on Zenodo** is the responsibility of the EB and only needs Project Coordinator approval when major components of the project may be affected in a critical way or when eventual knowledge protection possibilities (patents, utility models) are at stake. Any partner is encouraged to suggest and deliver contents and material to the Project Manager.
- **Partners' external communication:** Project related public information may be published on any partner's public website or his external communication media without approval. However, it has to be ensured that the sources are correctly acknowledged and that clear reference to NEWSERA and its public communication resources is indicated. Latest information must always be available for the NEWSERA web page and other coordinated public project information media.
- **Press and public relations:** Press releases and other press communication, as stated above, being publications, do not need approval. However, prior notification shall also go to the WP Leader of WP6 to check on alignment with the Project (dissemination strategy; breaches of confidentiality) in collaboration with the EB. In any case a review process is suggested.

- **Ethical issues:** In any communication outside the confidential environment of the project, the interest of third parties has to be respected. This is particularly important in the case of personal data, where informed consent for dissemination has to be obtained at the point of collection, even when information will be strongly de-personalized (see D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 on ethics requirements).
- **Project publication register:** All NEWSERA related public communication made shall be notified to the EB in order to maintain up-to-date news and a complete register of dissemination and publication activities. The EB will provide mechanisms for submitting information on latest publications.

3.2 Publication review

No approval is necessary for public disclosure of own knowledge related to NEWSERA (for example, publications or presentations) by any group of NEWSERA partners and it is in the high interest of the Consortium to facilitate project dissemination. Nevertheless, some check is required to guarantee the right of protection of knowledge for other Consortium partners. In other words, no quality control or review is necessary (although it may be desired and could then be organized by the authors), but reasonable time has to be given to the Partners (and, in some cases, to the EC) to check if their property (information or knowledge) or interests (in the case of the EC) is handled correctly or may be hurt. In such case, correction or withdrawal of such knowledge or information, or, where necessary, withdrawal of the publication, may be requested before final publication. This means that, although the final publication or presentation may not be ready to be distributed to any Partner or the EC since the very last moment before the submission deadline, still there must be at least 20 days for a Partner (after or before the deadline) to check the intended publication in detail before it finally goes public.

Where circumstances do not allow following the suggested procedure (e.g. invitation to present about the project less than 20 days prior to the presentation date) the presentation or publication need to be exclusively based on previously published or cleared information, to avoid conflicts. The EB will evaluate creating a repository of cleared material on the Google Drive shared workspace.

Important recommendation: The authors of a publication are most likely well aware of any potential conflict of interest arising from the disclosure of knowledge and critical information owned by others. It is therefore highly recommendable and in the interest of all involved to proactively clarify any issue with the partners involved, before the below procedure is started.

The **necessary steps for publication check** are fixed in the Article 29 of the EC Grant Agreement and in section 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement. In summary the following procedure applies:

- 1) For reasons of information and control, project partners have the right to learn about any planned publications with 20 days prior notice allowing them to exercise their right of objection if they consider the publication to harm the protection of their knowledge.
- 2) The Party or Parties wishing to make the publication, provide through the Main Author and by email, information on the planned abstract, publication or oral presentation to the Project Manager who informs immediately the Consortium (also by email, indicating in the header of the message the keyword [NEWSERA intended publication]). The information should at least include the foreseen list of authors, title, destination (where to publish), an idea of the content (e.g. abstract or reduced abstract) and the purpose of the publication (e.g. “publication of first results of WPX within the NEWSERA project”). All the Partners check the material to identify conflicts of interests through use or publication of their confidential information, Background, Foreground or similar.
- 3) Any Partner may request within the 20 days of the notification a copy of the information, which needs to be provided by the beneficiary planning to publish its knowledge to the requesting Party within 3 days from the receipt of the request.
- 4) The requesting Party’s right to object can then be exercised within 5 days from receipt of the copy. The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. The objecting Party cannot request a publication delay.
- 5) Parties affected by the disclosure of their knowledge are entitled to request that their proprietary confidential information, background and foreground, is deleted from any such publication or communication, if they consider that the protection of their Knowledge would be adversely affected.
- 6) The Main Author informs EB when contribution is accepted for publishing or has been presented publicly, for monitoring and documentation purposes of dissemination activities (adequate mechanisms will be provided by the EB).

3.3 Review of press releases

Press releases are an important component of project dissemination. The EB will provide a model for press releases on the Google Drive shared work space. A press release may be initiated by any project partner in agreement with the overall dissemination plan. All press releases should be reviewed by the Project Coordinator and the WP Leader of WP6 to check the overall message and coordinate with other project dissemination activities. Apart from that, Press Releases shall follow the same procedure as scientific publications.

3.4 Authorship and acknowledgement: Policy disclaimer

The authorship policy for scientific publications follows common practice in the scientific world and shall include co-authors that contributed actively in a

particular publication and developers that carried out significant work on which the particular publication reports. All publications or public material that report on or include material from activities carried out within the NEWSERA project (i.e. include results from activities charged fully or in-part against the NEWSERA project) shall expressly acknowledge that developments were made within NEWSERA and acknowledge the financial contribution made by the European Commission by means of the following acknowledgement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873125.

OR

The research described in this paper is partly supported by the project NEWSERA, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873125. The opinions expressed in it are those of the authors and are not necessarily those of the NEWSERA partners or the European Commission.

With that, the presented foreground is exclusively or partially assigned to the project with all contractual consequences like IPR and confidentiality, and is officially declared project output.

3.4.1 Citation format

To cite NEWSERA's deliverables and documents, the following should be used:

Surname, initials, Surname, initials, etc. (Year). Dx.x title. Deliverable report of project H2020 NEWSERA (grant agreement No 873125).

3.5 Project website

The official project website [newsera2020.eu] is managed by the WP6 Leader, Formicablu. It shall be the most up-to-date and complete reference for any project related public information. That means partners need to contribute with their latest materials as soon as the project advances, should make reference to it on their public communications and should provide WP6 Leader with news and latest facts such as complete information (date, place, media, source or reference, purpose, contents, etc.) on publications, press releases, public communication and presentations, amongst others. The WP6 Leader will facilitate the information submission with easy-to-use mechanisms such as, for example, simple standardized forms on the Google Drive shared work space.

Citizen science as the new paradigm for science communication

We want to integrate citizen science in science communication, as a tool to open up science and innovation to society and promote science literacy.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

3.6 Newsletters and Social Media

NEWSERA will have its own plan (see D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan and D6.6 for more information on wider dissemination plans and management of newsletters and social media). The hashtag #NEWSERA will be used and common dissemination actions will be promoted with SwafS-19 sister projects.

3.7 Regular cross-dissemination and meetings

The Project Coordinator will pay strong attention to eventual cross-dissemination and meetings to foster communication with related project within the same specific EC work programme, organised by the European Commission. **NEWSERA takes into account that there are six, so far, projects funded in 2018 and 2019 under H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 (Science with and for Society) Topic 19**, and that they will benefit from cooperation in certain areas - these projects being: QUEST, RETHINK, TRESKA, ParCos and CONCISE up to now. **The EC has requested these consortia to seek out opportunities for cooperation and common meetings have already started to establish those opportunities.**

3.8 Ethical and legal issues in dissemination

This section refers to the handling of personal data information outside the research and development tasks but inside the dissemination activities of NEWSERA. See Article 39 in the EC Grant Agreement.

Partners are requested to take the following points into consideration:

- Information disseminated should be in de-personalised form as a matter of security and confidentiality. Research beneficiaries should be informed of this, and the form of depersonalisation;
- Only as much information should be disclosed as is necessary for the purpose for which it is disclosed. Information should be destroyed when it is no longer needed for research purposes;
- Partners using information provided by other partners should check with those partners on ethical restrictions on the use of that information;
- Partners introducing/generating information encumbered by ethical restrictions are obliged to understand the extent and impact of those restrictions and inform other partners within the Consortium when providing them such information;
- As a particular issue, project developments creating data repositories should include a strategy for handling ethically encumbered information (e.g. separation of information according to options for use, destruction of resources post-project, inclusion of access control linked to the use limitations). Support during the development of such strategies will be available from the EB;
- In case of doubts of personal information registry and policies to be applied, the EB should be contacted for support at the earliest opportunity.

The implications of GDPR should also be considered as relevant, and as the rights of all EU citizens. GDPR includes but is not limited to:

- fair and transparent collecting, recording, storing, using, analysing, combining, disclosing or deleting of personal information;
- only as much data as necessary should be collected in the least obtrusive, but also most transparent, manner as possible;
- only processing data for purposes for which it was provided;
- adequate security measures;
- incident response plans; and documentation of your decisions and practises

Details about ethical and data management can be found at D7.1, D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 and are going to be updated at D7.2.

4 Managerial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The goal of Managerial Performance Indicators is to achieve the NEWSERA project vision and mission. A set of Key Performance Indicators have been developed for project internal management and monitoring.

Periodic activity reports will report on these indicators to assess whether there is evidence that quality-related activities are being performed effectively in the project and, if not, then implement corrective actions. **D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan also defines a set of dissemination KPIs for the communication and dissemination activities.**

The following paragraphs provided details on the four managerial KPIs:

- 1) Accurate use of resources / execution of budget**
- 2) Compliance of procedures**
- 3) Periodic reports and EC project review outcomes**
- 4) Milestones assessment**

4.1 Accurate use of resources / execution of budget

Description

Project beneficiaries must be able to evaluate the amount of effort they spend on the project. The coordinator and the EB must also have a good continuous view on the budget utilisation of each partner and must have access to information and numbers required for the reports the Commission requests (the description of the research progress and the description of technical and scientific achievements -not involved in the KPIs- are important components of these reports). The Commission asks the coordination of the project to report periodically on Work Packages advancement and the pace of the EC's grant utilisation.

Evaluation

The use of resources and budget consumption will be monitored during the project life: the collected data serves as basis for synthesis work carried out and forwarded to the Commission after approval by the EB.

The Project Coordinator will implement a reporting schedule and templates to monitor the use of resources and their accuracy with the project objectives fulfilment on a regular basis, as explained in previous sections. Above 20% deviation from expected figures based on these reports will result in the creation of deviation plans. The reports are to be completed within 1 month after the corresponding reporting period.

Reporting and Monitoring tools

The Project Coordinator will provide standardised forms allowing for:

- Efficient collection of information needed
 - Minimum effort and time spent

- Easy production of reporting and contractual documentation
 - By using an embedded approach

Regular inputs from each Organization:

- Web-based reports collection tool - standardised form
- A few lines per activity (technical achievement per WP)
- Validated by the WP Leaders

Summary from each WP:

- Collated (with eventual comments) by the WP leader

Summary per Partner:

- Validated by the WP Leaders
- Web-based recap spreadsheets

4.2 Compliance of procedures

Description

NEWSERA's project structure was kept intentionally simple, avoiding standing committees, thematic subteams or working groups. Following this line, the main responsibilities stand on the EB, WP Leaders and the Project Coordinator, responsible for exchanging and deciding on technical development and progress of work with a high frequency of contact and strategic project management issues. Due to the sensitivity and high interdependency of the work carried out in the different WPs, the Project Coordinator play an important role as coordinator and facilitator of communication, moderator of debates and controller of Objectives and Work Plan.

Evaluation criteria

- Timely delivery and quality assessment of deliverables and periodic reports
- Risks clearages

Reporting and Monitoring tools

Establishment of any advisory committees or ad hoc boards for matters that require specific attention and follow-up, including agreement on appointment and revocation of appointment of its members and establishment of their working procedures.

On periodic basis:

- revision of the Work Plan and approval thereof, as proposed by the EB.

- submit a proposal to the EB regarding the effort and budget allocation to partners, activities and work packages for the next reporting period.

4.3 Periodic reports and project reviews EC outcomes

Description

The Project Coordinator is responsible of the follow-up of activities and monitoring of compliance with the Project Work Plan, planned resources and time schedule, liaising with the EB, promoting as far as possible the synergy between different activities and efficiency throughout and the financial management, including the check for viability of the proposals of funding assignment to Project participants and activities submitted by the Work Package Leaders.

These responsibilities are assessed by the production of administrative and financial reporting periods, according to that is specified in the EC contract.

The reporting is accompanied with Reviews realised by the Project Officer and/or designated experts and will take place periodically. The encounters, besides reflection on the work done and outlook on work due shall also enable to demonstrate the progress of work.

Preventive actions

- Continuous evaluation of work progress and resources available.
- Early identification of potential difficulties and deviations from the work plan.
- Risk clearance, analysis and assessment.
- Design and implementation of remedial actions and recommendations (if necessary)
- Provide researchers, administrative staff, work package and tasks leaders, and the EB with all the required information and its processing, while keeping the time to update it to the bare minimum.
- Greatly facilitate the writing of the sensitive chapters of the numerous project reports, by including easy to access numerical information.
- Inform researchers and administrative staff on the whole project activities and on the efforts in each activity.

4.4 Milestones assessment

Description

Project' milestones shall be understood as assessment of expected achievements and will be used as points of critical analysis and reflection of work done and work to do. They provide additional points to check progress reflect the success of work and project implementation so far and plan the upcoming phase of the project.

Evaluation criteria

- Clear and concise background and results presented
- The main features of the item under consideration are identified and the associated issues are assessed
- Material and results issued are appropriately referenced

Reporting and Monitoring tools

Two weeks after the milestone deadline, formal reports are to be submitted from the WP Leaders to the EB, in which all exceptions to the previously-agreed schedule are highlighted, reviewed and explained, and the steps to be taken for risk amelioration and a return to the planned schedule are presented. In the event that the actions proposed so require, a formal discussion at the next EB teleconference will be held, during which the relevant issues will be reviewed and ratified accompanied by recommendations for action or improvement. The Project Manager will provide templates.

5 Appendix

Partners of the NEWSERA Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

List of beneficiaries			
Full name	Short name	Country	
SCIENCE FOR CHANGE, SL	SfC	Spain	
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNIPD	Italy	
FCIENCIAS.ID - ASSOCIACAO PARA A INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO DE CIENCIAS	FC.ID	Portugal	
FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGÍA, F.S.P.	FECYT	Spain	
FUNDACION IBERCIVIS	IBERCIVIS	Spain	
FORMICABLU SRL	FORMICABLU	Italy	

Table 2. Consortium members list

Deliverables of the NEWSERA are also referred to herein according to the following numbers:

D#	Deliverable Title	WP	Leader	Type	Diss level	Date
D1.1	Project Management handbook	WP1	SfC	Report	Public	M6
D1.2	Quality, Risk and Contingency Management Plan	WP1	SfC	Report	Public	M6
D1.3	Periodic report on interactions with Sounding Board members 1	WP1	SfC	Report	Confidential	M15
D1.4	Periodic report on interactions with Sounding Board members 2	WP1	SfC	Report	Confidential	M36
D2.1	Portrait of citizen	WP2	UNIPD	Report	Confidential	M12

science communication strategies in EU citizen science projects

D2.2	Report on indicators for impact assessment of science communication in citizen science projects	WP2	UNIPD	Report	Public	M13
D2.3	Effectiveness of science communication in EU citizen science projects	WP2	IBERCIVIS	Report	Public	M15
D3.1	Description of #CitSciComm Labs	WP3	SfC	Report	Confidential	M15
D3.2	Co-designed innovative strategies for Citizen Science Communication 1	WP3	UNIPD	Report	Confidential	M15
D3.3	Co-designed innovative strategies for Citizen Science Journalism 1	WP3	FORMICABLU	Report	Confidential	M15
D3.4	Co-designed innovative strategies for Citizen Science Communication 2	WP3	UNIPD	Report	Confidential	M30
D3.5	Co-designed innovative strategies for Citizen Science Journalism 2	WP3	FORMICABLU	Report	Confidential	M30
D3.6	Formal and informal training mechanisms for science communication	WP3	FC.ID	Report	Confidential	M31
D3.7	Citizen Science as a communication tool in the Post-Factual Era	WP3	FECYT	Report	Public	M33
D4.1	Description of #CitSciComm Pilots	WP4	SfC	Report	Confidential	M19
D4.2	Blueprint for #CitSciComm with and for Citizen Scientists and society at large	WP4	UNIPD	Report	Public	M33
D4.3	Blueprint for #CitSciComm with and for Career Scientists	WP4	FC.ID	Report	Public	M33
D4.4	Blueprint for	WP4	FECYT	Report	Public	M33

	#CitSciComm with and for Policy Makers					
D4.5	Blueprint for #CitSciComm with and for Industry and SMEs	WP4	SfC	Report	Public	M33
D4.6	Blueprint for #CitSciComm with and for Science Journalists	WP4	FORMICABLU	Report	Public	M33
D5.1	Iteration Cycle I and II: Impact assessment of the new communication strategies for each stakeholder group	WP5	IBERCIVIS	Report	Confidential	M26
D5.2	Iteration Cycle III & IV: Impact assessment of new communication strategies for each stakeholder group	WP5	IBERCIVIS	Report	Confidential	M34
D5.3	Guide of Science Communication in Citizen Science Projects and Citizen Science Journalism	WP5	FECYT	Report	Public	M35
D5.4	NEWSERA Policy Briefs 2	WP5	FECYT	Report	Public	M35
D5.5	NEWSERA Policy Briefs 1	WP5	FECYT	Report	Public	M15
D6.1	Events 1	WP6	FORMICABLU	Report	Public	M3
D6.2	Dissemination and Communication Plan	WP6	FORMICABLU	Report	Confidential	M6
D6.3	NEWSERA Visual Identity	WP6	FORMICABLU	Website	Public	M6
D6.4	NEWSERA project official video	WP6	FORMICABLU	Website	Public	M6
D6.5	Events 2	WP6	FORMICABLU	Report	Public	M13
D6.6	Updated Dissemination and Communication Plan	WP6	FORMICABLU	Report	Confidential	M24
D6.7	Events 3	WP6	FORMICABLU	Report	Public	M25
D7.1	Data Management Plan	WP7	IBERCIVIS	ORDP	Confidential	M6
D7.2	Report on ethics aspects as a cross-cutting issue in NEWSERA actions	WP7	IBERCIVIS	Report	Public	M18

D8.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP8 SfC	Ethics	Confidential M6
D8.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2	WP8 SfC	Ethics	Confidential M6
D8.3	H - POPD - Requirement No. 3	WP8 SfC	Ethics	Confidential M6

Table 3. NEWSERA Deliverables list